

ATTITUDE OF COLLEGE STUDENTS TOWARDS ONLINE LEARNING DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Dr. Anita Verma

Associate Professor, Dronacharya College of Education, Rait, Kangra (H.P)

Email- anitadronacharya@gmail.com

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Abstract

Education is the building block of any nation; it builds skills, habits, knowledge and mindset of students. A strong educational system not only nurtures competent students but also contributes to the overall progress of a nation. Along with education, health remains a major concern for every country, and safeguarding the well-being of citizens is a fundamental responsibility of the government. The outbreak of COVID-19, declared a Public Health Emergency of International concern by the World Health Organization (WHO), brought unprecedented challenges to various sectors, particularly education. The present study attempts to examine the attitude of college students towards online learning in relation to gender, type of institution (government and private), location (rural and urban), and stream (science and arts). A survey method was employed to collect data from 200 college students of Kangra District of Himachal Pradesh, using an attitude scale. The data collected through the scale was analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. The findings revealed that there is no significant difference in the attitude of college students towards online learning with respect to gender, location, and type of institution. However, a significant difference is observed in the attitude of Science and Arts stream college students towards online learning.

Keywords: Covid-19, Educational system, College students, Online learning

Introduction:

Education plays an important role in building the nation. In India, various steps were taken by government after independence to make education available to all. Every aspect of human life is affected by education directly or indirectly. The government of India has formulated several committees and commissions, which recommended various important steps to improve the quality of education in India. The 21st century is said to be the age of science and technology. The process of communication among people has increased so rapidly due to the use of internet. The world is being a family with the help of new

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technology. Scientific inventions has influenced every aspect of human life. Science and technology have achieved an important place in present-day society. Science and technology is used in all areas- hospitals, banks, industries, etc. Its success is also generalized to the teaching-learning situation, which makes teaching-learning systematic, effective and faster. The computer and laboratory are now being used in the teaching-learning process. With the help of technology, the relationship between the teachers and students is being made friendly. One can access any type of needed information easily with the help of technology. As well as one can share his knowledge with others so that others can be benefited from it. To use the internet in the teaching-learning process, a concept emerged as online learning, which helps the learners to access knowledge anytime and anywhere. Online learning helps people to learn anything by using modern technology. It has become more popular and gaining wide acceptance as a ‘non-traditional’ mode of learning at all levels of education starting from primary to higher education. All the educational institutions have adopted online learning to enhance skills and knowledge to improve the quality of education. It also offers opportunities to the nation to develop educationally as well as economically. In all educational institutions using the internet and other smart appliances in the form of e-learning has become an indispensable part, as it has gained a specific place in the teaching-learning process. Smart electronic gadgets like mobiles, laptops, and computers also play a very significant role in productive teaching-learning. The structure of the educational process is being maintained and the nature of the educational process is also improved through e-learning. The scenario of teaching-learning is quite changed due to the Covid-19 pandemic period. It snatches the normal livelihood of a person. Thus, the prevalent classroom teaching also changed at every level viz., schools, higher education, coaching, and certifications (Bansal & Mehera, 2021).

Online Learning:

A Learning system based on formalized teaching but with the help of the internet and e-resources is known as online learning. All the learning instructions, assessments and evaluations are done through the virtual environment. It is another form of distance and open learning; it can take the form of synchronous and asynchronous learning. Computer-based training, Web-based training, Internet-based training, online training, online learning (electronic learning), m-learning (mobile learning), computer-aided distance education-online education goes by many names and comes in a variety of styles, but at its core: “Online education is electronically supported learning that relies on the Internet for

teacher/student interaction and the distribution of class materials.” Online learning has shown significant growth over the last decade, as the internet and education combine to provide people with the opportunity to gain new skills. With the emergence of COVID-19, online learning has gained significant importance in people’s lives. The pandemic has forced schools, universities, and companies to remote work and this booms the usage of online learning.

Online learning has emerged as a significant paradigm in modern education, characterized by the integration of digital technologies, internet connectivity, and interactive platforms to facilitate teaching and learning processes. It encompasses a broad range of instructional practices, including web-based courses, virtual classrooms, blended learning environments, and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs). The evolution of online learning reflects the dynamic intersection of pedagogy and technology, reshaping educational access, delivery, and evaluation across global contexts. The global significance of online learning was particularly evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, when educational institutions shifted abruptly to remote instruction to ensure continuity of education. Reports by UNESCO (2020) indicated that over 1.5 billion learners worldwide were affected by school closures, accelerating the adoption of digital education. This unprecedented transition highlighted both the potential and the challenges of online learning, including issues related to digital divide, learner engagement, and instructional effectiveness. Online learning encompasses the process of gaining knowledge and skills by participating in educational activities that occur either in real-time or at different times, using different devices such as smart phones and computers, as long as there is an internet connection. Within these settings, students have the freedom to learn and engage with instructors and peers from any location, without being dependent on a specific physical space (Singh & Thurman, 2019).

Review of the Related Literature:

Afroz (2021), Conducted a study on “Students and Teachers’ Attitude towards Online class during Covid-19 Pandemic”. The objective of the study was to investigate the students and teachers’ attitude towards online learning during the covid-19 situation in Bangladeshi Government Colleges. Methodology was the qualitative and quantitative research method with semi-structured interview conducted via zoom, Focus group discussion, Google Platform. Result reveals that all the students are enjoying but they are missing face-to-face classes. They also miss their friends, who lives in remote area of villages are unable to

attend the classes due to internet network problem. Teachers thought about students' attitude towards online learning is anti academic and there is a lack of seriousness in all cases. We can say their proper discipline and concentration is difficult in online learning.

Technol (2022), This study reveals that the three domains of OLSE—learning, time management, and technology-played salient roles in student satisfaction during the emergency shift to remote learning owing to the COVID-19 pandemic. Students' judgment of their ability to complete online courses is critical for providing a successful remote learning-based approach. These empirical findings add to the fundamental knowledge of both educators and decision-makers as a method of assessing academic self-efficacy in online learning environments. The results may also help instructors and the education sector provide proactive strategies and approaches to improve all domains of students' self-efficacy to embrace the dynamic remote learning-based approach. Institutions should take this opportunity to evaluate how well they implemented remote learning to maintain the continuity of education, especially under any crisis condition.

Akcil (2020), Concluded his study on online learning attitudes of students thought to affect their desire for continuing education. High-quality learning experience of students does not only result from the efforts of teachers in online learning (**Haznedar & Baran, 2012**). Readiness and characteristics of students are extremely important (**Simonson et al, 2009**).

Unger and Meiran (2020) researched the attitude of students towards online learning during the first few weeks of online learning implementation. In this survey, students expressed their anxiety towards online learning, disappointment about missing graduation ceremony, and felt the differences in standards of learning between campus learning and online learning. However, students expressed improvement in their learning and adaptability during follow up.

Need and Significance of the Study:

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, declared a global health emergency by the World Health Organization, brought an abrupt and transformative change in the global education system. Higher education institutions were compelled to suspend face-to-face classes and immediately shift to online modes of instruction to ensure continuity of learning. This sudden transition occurred without adequate planning, training, or infrastructure, thereby creating multiple academic and technological challenges for students. In such circumstances, it became essential to study the attitude of college students toward online learning, as attitude is a critical determinant of learning effectiveness, academic

engagement, and achievement. Many students faced issues such as poor internet connectivity, lack of digital devices, limited technical skills, and an uncondusive home environment, which influenced their learning experiences. The significance of this study lies in its ability to provide insights for improving online education practices, strengthening digital infrastructure, and supporting effective policy decisions. Understanding students' attitude helps educators and administrators identify both the strengths and limitations of online learning, thereby contributing to the development of more inclusive, flexible, and sustainable higher education systems in the future.

Statement of the Problem:

The research problem is entitled as “**Attitude of College Students towards Online learning during Covid-19 Pandemic.**”

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the attitude of college students towards online learning with respect to gender.
2. To study the attitude of college students towards online learning with respect to locality.
3. To study the attitude of college students towards online learning with respect to stream.
4. To study the difference in the attitude of govt. sponsored and private college students towards online learning.

Hypotheses of the Study:

1. There will be no significant difference in the attitude of male and female college students towards online learning.
2. There will be no significant difference in the attitude of urban and rural area college students towards online learning.
3. There will be no significant difference in the attitude of Arts and Science stream college students towards online learning.
4. There will be no significant difference in the attitude of Government and Private college students towards online learning.

Methodology:

The Present study is descriptive in nature. Responses of a sample of 200 college students selected from Kangra district of Himachal Pradesh through convenient sampling technique were recorded. The attitude scale was used, which consists of 30 items each has 5 alternatives, whereas the students have to tick against any one option according to their views. The responses are 1 for strongly disagree, 2 for disagree, 3for neutral, 4 for agree and 5 for strongly agree. Mean, Median, Mode, Standard deviation, t-test have been used to

analyze the data. The study has made the use of only primary data for achieving the objectives of the study.

Testing of the Hypotheses:

Hypothesis1: There will be no significant difference in the attitude of male and female college students towards online learning.

Table-1, Comparison of the difference in attitude of Male and Female college students

Variable			Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t - value
Attitude towards Online learning			Male	70	86.29	7.66	0.24(NS)
			Female	130	84.89	8.26	

NS denotes not significant

****denote significant at 0.01 level**

***denotes significant at 0.05 level**

The data presented in Table-1 indicates that male students ($M = 86.29$, $SD = 7.66$, $N = 70$) have a slightly higher mean score on attitude towards online learning compared to female students ($M = 84.89$, $SD = 8.26$, $N = 130$). However, the calculated t -value (0.24) is not statistically significant at either the 0.05 or 0.01 level of significance. This means that the observed difference in mean scores between male and female students is very small and may have occurred due to chance rather than representing a real difference in attitude. Since the obtained t -value is less than the critical value required for significance, the difference is considered statistically non-significant (NS). Therefore; the null hypothesis stating that “There is no significant difference in the attitude of male and female college students towards online learning” is accepted.

Hypothesis2: There will be no significant difference in the attitude of Science and Arts stream college students towards online learning.

Table-2, Comparison of difference in attitude of Science and Arts stream college students

Variable			Stream	N	Mean	S.D	t -Value
Attitude towards Online			Science	137	89.7	7.72	2.84**
			Arts	133	89.2	7.72	

learning	Arts	63	84.38	9.17
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NS denotes not significant

****denote significant at 0.01 level**

***denotes significant at 0.05 level**

Table-2 shows that Science stream students ($M = 89.72$, $SD = 7.72$, $N = 137$) have a higher mean attitude score towards online learning compared to Arts stream students ($M = 84.38$, $SD = 9.17$, $N = 63$). The mean difference between the two groups is 5.34, which indicates a noticeable variation in their attitudes. The calculated t -value (2.84) is significant at the 0.01 level of significance. This means that the observed difference in attitudes between Science and Arts students is statistically significant and not due to chance. Since the obtained t -value is significant at the 0.01 level, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. Therefore, it is concluded that there is a significant difference between Science and Arts stream college students in their attitude towards online learning.

Hypothesis3: There will be no significant differences in the attitude of rural and urban college students towards online learning.

Table-3, Comparison of the difference in attitude of Rural and Urban college students

Variable	Locality	N	Mean	S.D	t-value
Attitude towards Online learning	Rural	137	85.23	8.34	0.70(NS)
	Urban	63	85.70	7.48	

NS denotes not significant

****denote significant at 0.01 level**

***denotes significant at 0.05 level**

The data presented in Table 3 reveal that the mean attitude score of urban students ($M = 85.70$, $SD = 7.48$, $N = 63$) is slightly higher than that of rural students ($M = 85.23$, $SD = 8.34$, $N = 137$). However, the difference in mean scores is very minimal (0.47), indicating almost identical levels of attitude toward online learning in both groups. The calculated t -value (0.70) is not significant at either the 0.05 or 0.01 levels of significance. This indicates that the observed difference between rural and urban students is statistically non-significant and may have occurred due to chance rather than representing a real difference. Since the obtained t -value is lower than the critical value required for significance, the null hypothesis

(H₀₃) is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that locality (rural or urban background) does not significantly influence college students' attitudes towards online learning in the present study

Hypothesis 4: There will be no significant difference in the attitude of Govt. and Private college students towards online learning

Table-4, Comparison of the difference in attitude of Govt. and Private College students

Variable	Type of Institutions	N	Mean	S.D	t-value
Attitude towards Online learning	Private	152	85.01	7.59	0.25(NS)
	Govt.	48	86.54	9.39	

NS denotes not significant

****denote significant at 0.01 level**

***denotes significant at 0.05 level**

The data in Table 4 shows that Government college students (M = 86.54, SD = 9.39, N = 48) have a slightly higher mean attitude score towards online learning compared to Private college students (M = 85.01, SD = 7.59, N = 152). The mean difference between the two groups is 1.53, which is relatively small. This indicates that the observed difference in mean scores is very minimal and may have occurred due to chance rather than representing a real difference between the two groups. Since the obtained *t*-value is much lower than the critical value required for significance, the null hypothesis (H₀₄) is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that the type of institution (Government or Private) does not significantly influence the attitude of college students towards online learning.

Findings:

The findings of the present study reveal that gender does not have a statistically significant influence on college students' attitudes towards online learning. The difference in mean scores between male and female students was found to be non-significant, indicating that gender does not influence students' attitude towards online learning. Similarly, no significant difference was observed between rural and urban students, suggesting that locality does not significantly affect students' attitudes towards online learning. In the same manner, the comparison between Government and Private College students also yielded a non-significant result, implying that the type of institution does not contribute meaningfully to variations in students' attitudes. However, a statistically significant difference was found

between Science and Arts stream students. Science students demonstrated a significantly more favorable attitude towards online learning than Arts students, and the difference was significant at the 0.01 level. This finding indicates that academic stream is an important variable influencing students' attitudes towards online learning. Thus, it can be concluded that among the selected demographic variables, only academic stream has a significant impact on college students' attitudes towards online learning, whereas gender, locality, and type of institution do not exert a statistically significant influence in the context of the present study.

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